

TESTING AND FAILURE ANALYSIS OF A CFRP WINGBOX CONTAINING A 150J IMPACT

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SUMMARY: This paper describes the mechanical testing and failure analysis of a multispar CFRP wingbox which was subjected to 150J impact on a spar foot. The wingbox was loaded in bending to failure, with the impacted skin under compressive load. The structure failed at the impact site at a strain of $-3900\mu\epsilon$; a load intensity of 1170kN/m. The first event was delamination growth near the backface which was driven along interfaces containing 90° plies, followed by formation of a narrow band of delaminations close to the upper surface. Skin delamination extended parallel to the spars whilst delaminations developed close to and within the spar feet. Finally, the skin and spars failed in compression. This work has improved the understanding of failure in large composite structures containing impact damage and demonstrated read across between structural elements and full-scale structural tests.

KEYWORDS: Wingbox, Structural Test, Fractography, Impact, Delamination, Compression.

INTRODUCTION

Potential low cost and high specific properties have led to aircraft structures now containing a high proportion of fibre reinforced composite. Impact is one of the critical threats to such structures and tolerance to impact is a key design requirement. An impact can introduce damage which will reduce the mechanical performance, particularly under compressive loading. In service, composite structures will experience severe impacts but will be expected to still carry load, albeit under less demanding conditions; there is a need to understand the performance of structures containing damage induced by such impacts. Most of the work done to date has considered impacts in coupons and structural elements. However, in large structures, factors such as structural response and the local sub-structure affect the damage growth and final failure. How to use the knowledge gleaned from coupon and element tests to predict the behaviour of large, full-scale structures is poorly understood.

The aim of this programme was to improve the understanding of impact damage in large composite structures. A wingbox (Figure 1) was designed, built and impact tested, the results of which are described elsewhere [1]. The aim of the work reported here was to understand the failure of a large composite structure containing extensive impact damage. A very large impact (150J) was introduced to the surface of the structure which was then tested to failure in

bending; the impacted face was loaded in compression. After failure, the wingbox was analysed using fractographic techniques to deduce the detailed failure processes.

Figure 1 Photograph of the CFRP Wingbox in the Loading Frame

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS AND STRUCTURAL TESTING

The wingbox was entirely fabricated from CFRP (Hexel T800/924) and, although the design was generic, it was based on a fighter wing. The skin thickness tapered from 7mm (at the root) to 4mm (at the tip) with a quasi-isotropic lay-up. The structure was 1.8m long and 0.8m wide with the skins attached to six spars; the lower skin was bolted whilst the upper skin was bonded. As viewed from the root, the spars were numbered from the right (spar #1) to the left (spar #6) side of the box. The structure was clamped at the root and loaded at the tip in bending. As reported elsewhere [1], a number of low energy impacts were introduced and the effect of parameters such as energy, location and preload were characterised. Finally, a large impact (150J) was introduced over a spar foot, 250mm from the root. This energy level was close to the FAA airworthiness requirement of 100 ft.lb (136J) [2]. The drop height and tup diameter were 1.3m and 12.7mm, and testing was carried out using an instrumented drop-weight impactor with a mass of 11.57kg; these conditions were chosen to maintain consistency with earlier work [1]. This site was chosen because earlier studies [1] had shown that damage at this location would be likely to cause the greatest reduction in the strength; this site experienced the highest strains. The wingbox was instrumented to record the load, displacements and strain variation across the width and along the length of both skins.

Prior to testing the impact site was characterised using a pulse-echo ultrasonic system. The structure was tested to failure in displacement control with the impacted face under compression. The wingbox was then dissected and analysed using fractographic techniques to deduce the failure processes. After post-failure ultrasonic inspection, the damaged region of the upper skin and spars was removed to allow a detailed examination. The removed section included the entire width of the wingbox and encompassed all the damage generated during the final failure; a length of about 400mm. This damaged region was then sectioned parallel to the spars along the centre of each bay, giving six sections which were then examined individually.

The edges of each of the sections were lightly polished and, with reference to the stacking sequence, the positions of the major delaminations were identified. The major delaminated surfaces were then levered open to expose the fracture surfaces. Firstly, low power microscopy was used to study the surfaces; the failure modes, growth directions and failure sequences were deduced using standard fractographic techniques. These findings were then verified using electron microscopy. When all the failure surfaces had been characterised, the overall failure sequence of the wingbox was deduced.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND FAILURE ANALYSIS

Impact and Mechanical Testing

A photograph and ultrasonic scan of the impact site on the upper skin are shown in Figure 2. The site consisted of a circular indentation about 20mm in diameter containing fibre fracture and matrix splitting. In the ultrasonic scan the dotted black lines indicate the positions of the spar foot and centreline. The undamaged material is purple whilst the impact damage is orange and white (colours corresponding to different depths). The black disk is the penetrated region, beyond which the damage was elliptical in shape, extending for 100mm parallel to the spar and 67mm perpendicular to the spar; a damage area of 5260mm². The distribution of the damage was approximately conical with the largest delaminations towards the backface. The damage extended as far as the web of spar #3 and just into the bay between spars #3 and #4.

Figure 2 Photograph and Ultrasonic Scan of the 150J Impact Site

The wingbox failed at an applied load of 105kN; an average strain of $-3100\mu\epsilon$ on the surface of the skin. The measured strain peaked at $-3900\mu\epsilon$, close to the impact site, which was equivalent to a load per unit width in the upper skin of 1170kN/m. The strain then fell off towards the tip of the box and, 1350mm from the root, it had fallen to $-2000\mu\epsilon$. The tip deflected by about 80mm with a 1mm difference between the actuators which indicated that there was negligible twisting of the structure.

Description of the Failed Wingbox

The visible failure (Figure 3) to the box consisted of a narrow band of delamination and surface cracking which extended across most of the width (through the impact site) and into the spars. This band of fracture was about 60mm wide and was approximately perpendicular to the span of the box, except towards the left edge (spar #6) where it was displaced towards the root. This fracture was about 250mm from the root of the wingbox, almost coincident with a ply-drop-off in the skins. The failure mode was compressive but there was relatively little damage to the lower skin.

Figure 3 The Upper Skin of the Wingbox after Failure

The failure of the right edge of the box was dominated by an angled through-thickness crack in the upper skin and a Y-shaped crack in the spar (spar #1); the root of the Y was located in the upper spar cap, although it was not coincident with the failure in the skin. The surface plies exhibited multiple delamination and splitting which were only limited in extent. The failure of the left edge (spar #6) was very different; the skin had extensively delaminated, particularly close to the upper surface. There was also extensive delamination within the spar foot and a Y-shaped crack; the root of the Y was adjacent to the upper spar cap. The failure of the internal face of the upper skin consisted of surface delamination and splitting with some limited fracture of the surface fibres. The internal spars (#2 to #5) contained either straight fractures or Y-shaped cracks; blistering in the webs indicated that delamination was often the first event. In addition there was a lack of continuity between the skin and spar fractures, indicating that the spars had detached from the skin before failure.

The ultrasonic scan of the upper skin is shown in Figure 4; undamaged material is light whilst the damage is dark. The extent of the damage on the right side of the wingbox was considerably less than that on the left. On the right there was a central band of delamination which was 100mm at its widest point (between spars #2 and #3). Over the two outer spars on the right (spars #1 and #2), there were delaminations which extended along the spars, particularly on the tip side of the main fracture but there was only limited delamination within the impacted spar (spar #3). On the left side there was again delamination extending along the wingbox, particularly at spar #6, which extended for about 320mm. However, this side was

dominated by a wide band of delamination which extended from spar #3 to the left edge of the box, that was mainly on the root side of the main fracture.

Figure 4 Ultrasonic Scan (Defect Gated) of the Failure of the Upper Skin

Figure 5 Simplified Diagram of the Damage at the Main Failure of the Upper Skin

A diagram of the failure is shown in Figure 5; illustrating the position of the main delaminations or fractures coloured according to depth (the numbers in the key refer to the tipward ply interfaces of the damage). Each particular delamination was not limited to one ply interface, but usually two, connected via ply splits. The stacking sequence on the root side of the fracture was $[(+45^\circ/-45^\circ/+45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ)_4]_S$ whilst the stacking sequence on the tip side was the same, except the 10th and 39th plies (both -45°) had been removed.

The failure of the structure was quite complex, consisting of multiplane delamination, skin/spar detachment, skin compression failure and spar fracture. The damage from the initial impact (marked in red in Figure 5) was visible as an elliptical lobe of multiplane delamination mostly towards the back face. Across most of the width of the box (from the left edge to the centre of spar #2) was a narrow band of multiplane delaminations which were close to the upper surface (shown in grey in Figure 5). Exposure of these delaminated surfaces revealed that they were mainly mode I dominated fracture which had initiated near the impact site and spread across the structure towards the sides. These narrow delaminations were mainly at interfaces containing 90° plies and, from the surrounding fracture morphology, it was deduced that the formation of this band of delaminations was early in the failure process.

There was a large delamination on the left side of the box (marked in blue in Figure 5) which was at the plane of the ply-drop-off (36/37/38 ply interfaces on the tip side; $90^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ$). This damage extended between spars #6 and #3, encompassing the impact site. With respect to the main fracture, this delamination had extended about 75mm towards the tip and 200mm towards the root, encompassing the ply-drop-off. This fracture was relatively early in the fracture process and had initiated in the region of the impact site, spreading lengthwise along the structure, and towards the left edge. There was also a large delamination on the right side (shown in yellow in Figure 5) which extended between spar #3 and the right edge of the wingbox (encompassing the impact site). This delamination was relatively narrow, only extending up to 50mm either side of the main fracture. Exposure of the delaminated plies revealed this delamination was at the 15/16/17 ply interface ($-45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$), and had extended from the impact site towards the right edge.

There was evidence of multiplane delamination which extended from the sides of the structure (shown in green and orange in Figure 5). These delaminations were at 9/10/11 ($-45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$) and 24/25/26 ($90^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ$) ply interfaces respectively; the former contained a ply-drop-off. This damage had grown from the edges of the structure, towards the centre of the box. The detachment of the skin from the spars is shown in purple in Figure 5; in most regions the delamination was just within the skin at the 41/42/43 ply interface ($90^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ$). These delaminations were more extensive on the tipward side of the main failure, particularly on the edges (spars #1 and #6). These failures were dominated by mode II fracture, and had extended from the line of the main damage, towards the tip and the root of the box.

Most of the fibre fracture in the skin was compressive; it was deduced [3] that the failure had initiated at the impact site and had spread widthwise. From the morphology of this failure and the surrounding delaminations, it was clear this compression fracture had occurred late in the failure process, particularly with respect to the fractures on the left side. The failure of the spars are shown in Figure 5 as dashed lines; note they were not aligned, and not coincident with the main skin compression failure. This indicated that the spars had detached from the skin before they had failed. The failure of the spars was a combination of delamination in the webs, which initiated at the root of the spars adjacent to the upper skin, and compression fracture of the spar feet.

DISCUSSION

Sequence of Failure

The sequence of failure of the wingbox is illustrated in Figures 6 and 7. The former shows the initial fracture events whilst the latter illustrates the entire failure process.

Figure 6 Diagram of the Initial Damage Growth Mechanisms

The impact site and spars #3 and #4 are illustrated in Figure 6a. The initial damage growth began at the impact site, as delaminations (Figure 6b) which extended across the bay but were arrested at the web of spar #4 (Figure 6c). These delaminations initially occurred at a number of planes, but those which exhibited the most growth were close to the backface and grew within interfaces containing 90° plies. The delaminations were driven by local buckling of the delaminated plies towards the spars, which generated mode I (peel) forces transverse to the span of the wingbox. However, as the damage extended beneath the spars, the change in local geometry suppressed buckling and arrested the delamination growth. Consequently the site of the damage growth changed to near the upper layers of the skin, which felt less influence of the sub-structure (Figures 7a and 6d). Again, this damage was dominated by mode I, but with the plies buckling upwards (away from the spars). This band of delamination initiated near the impact site and spread to the right, up to spar #2, and up to the left edge of the wingbox, occurring at planes containing 90° plies.

Some delaminations from the impact damage exhibited further growth towards the root (Figure 7b). To the right of the impact site, this delamination was at the 15/16/17 ply interface and extended to the right edge of the wingbox. Similarly, to the left, massive delamination occurred at the 36/37/38 ply interface (containing a ply-drop off). The next event was probably delamination close to the backface and within the spar feet (Figure 7c). In addition, delaminations initiated along the edge of the wingbox and extended inwards. Eventually, compression failure of the skin (Figure 7d) initiated from the fibre damage at the impact site and extended across the entire width. On the right, in which there had only been limited delamination, the failure had an angled appearance characteristic of compressive failure in thick laminates [4]. However, on the left, the failure was indistinct ('green-stick') due to extensive delamination prior to compressive failure. Failure of the spars was probably the final event.

Figure 7 Sequence of Failure of the Wingbox

Discussion of Failure

The damage area (5260mm²) was well in excess of that observed for the lower energy impacts; for comparison, a 45J impact on the spar foot had an area of 2930mm² [1]. The structure failed at the impact site at a peak strain of -3900µε, which was a load intensity (load per unit width) of 1170kN/m in the upper skin. Current designs [5] require a design ultimate load (DUL) of 1500kN/m, with a limit load of two-thirds of this value. The 150J impact damage would have exceeded the requirement [6] for barely visible impact damage and would have been defined as clearly visible damage; *i.e.* the structure would need to withstand this damage between inspections. Under current aircraft requirements [6], the structure would have been required to withstand limit load when containing such damage; the wingbox withstood 117% of limit load. In comparison [7], in stiffened panels containing 15J impact damage in a stiffener foot (an area of 780mm²) had a strength of 2200kN/m (-5800µε), although these structures were loaded under compression rather than bending.

There was no evidence of interaction between the damage at the other impact sites and the damage growth from the 150J impact. In addition, there was no damage growth at any of the low energy impact sites during the test to failure. Both these findings are encouraging and demonstrate significant damage tolerance in a large composite structure.

Both the initial impact damage growth and the narrow band of delamination occurred at interfaces containing 90° plies; similar to the effects observed in plain and stiffened panels [4,7]. During delamination growth, the propagation direction is defined by the driving forces and local ply orientations; delaminations preferentially grow parallel to the fibre direction [4,8]. Mode I loading transverse to the spars was the main driving force, so growth preferentially occurred at the 90° plies. Minimising the number of 90° plies and ensuring they are deep within the laminate would help improve the damage tolerance.

One interesting feature was the preferential locations of the spar and skin delaminations; damage in the skin extended towards the root whilst damage close to the spars extended towards the tip. This was attributed to the loading conditions in a beam under bending [4,8]. The shear forces, generated by the bending of the structure, can be resolved into tensile and compressive forces. The fracture plane will be normal to the resolved tensile stress, and will be at an angle to the plane of the wingbox. Consequently, damage from the impact site will migrate upwards when growing towards the root, and migrate downwards when growing towards the tip.

Delamination growth was a key feature of the failure of this structure. The fractographic evidence showed that massive delamination had occurred at a number of planes prior to any significant compressive failure of the fibres. This indicates that modelling of such a failure should account for the initiation and growth mechanisms of this delamination.

CONCLUSIONS

An CRFP wingbox was impacted at 150J on a spar foot, 250mm from the root. The wingbox was loaded in bending, with the impacted face under compression until failure occurred. The results of this test were analysed and a detailed failure analysis conducted to determine the source and sequence of failure. From this study, the following conclusions were drawn.

1. There was no interaction between the damage at the low energy impact sites and the damage growth from the 150J impact during the test to failure which demonstrates significant damage tolerance in a large composite structure. However, the high energy impact gave a significant reduction in performance.
2. The wingbox failed at a peak surface strain of $-3900\mu\epsilon$ (a load intensity of 1170kN/m) which was just above current design requirements for clearly visible impact damage. The failure of the structure initiated at the impact site as mode I dominated damage growth which spread between the two central spars. This was followed by unstable growth of a narrow band of surface delamination across most of the width of the wingbox.
3. Extensive delamination developed towards the root; the largest of these was at the plane of a ply-drop-off and formed on the left side of the box. Delamination also developed close to and within the spar feet and extended towards the tip. Finally, the skin and spars failed in compression.
4. The primary damage growth mechanisms in the wingbox were very similar to those observed in smaller structural elements tests. In particular, the initial damage growth was dominated by mode I forces, at interfaces containing 90° plies and the sub-structure impeded delamination growth. The results of this work demonstrate the need across between structural elements and full-scale structural tests.

5. The benefits of this work are an improved understanding of the failure of full scale composite structures containing impact damage. This will lead to improved structures capable of tolerating damage, reduced certification costs for composite structures, and consequently reduced procurement costs and timescales.

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